

Complex Probabilities in Free Particle Quantum Mechanics Part 3

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In Part 1, we suggested that in one dimensional reflection-refraction from an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction at $x=0$, one may write a continuity equation for various $\exp(ipx)$ s as well as one for its first derivative d/dx , i.e. $A\exp(ipx)+B\exp(-ipx) = C\exp(ip_2x)$ at $x=0$ and $pA \exp(ipx) - pB\exp(-ipx) = Cp_2 \exp(ip_2x)$ at $x=0$. Here A , B and C are the fluxes of the incident, reflected and refracted waves. We argued that the incident photon contains an inherent probability $\exp(ipx)$ which means there is uncertainty in x for p hits. Nevertheless, one mathematically forces continuity at $x=0$. Given that $\exp(ipx)$ is a math function, one must be concerned with mathematical continuity, but there should also be a physical view. $\exp(ipx)$ seems to imply that p may interact within a wavelength region of \hbar/p (as in an interaction with both slits of a 2-slit apparatus when the slits are about a wavelength apart), so it seems that one must consider that physically there may be a small region dx in which one is not sure whether one has an incident, reflected or refracted photon. We have suggested this in previous notes. In particular, we argued that one may set the junction at $x=0$ or at $x=0+dx$ in such a scenario, giving rise to the continuity of the derivative d/dx equation.

The point we wish to make here is that there seems to be an inherent stochastic property of the incident photon in space and this means an interaction must be treated stochastically considering a resonance of the incident, reflected and refracted photon together. This leads to the weights A, B, C and one finds that for $n_1 < n_2$, that $B < 0$. We suggested in Part 2 that this means a phase $\exp(i\pi) = -1$ is introduced in the reflected photon and that this is linked to a physical property, as such a photon will interfere with another also with $-p$, but no phase. If the reflected photon interferes with such a photon, we argue here that it interacts with the incident photon because one has the uncertainty x (of dx). Thus, $A+B=C$ is actually physically created in a physical-stochastic manner (resonance) as the probability is no longer a math function, but is linked with an inherent stochasticity $\exp(ipx)$ which is physical. This, in turn, may induce a phase shift in $\exp(ipx)$ s in order to ensure that $\exp(ipx)$ equations are continuous at $x=0$ and $x=0+dx$, or the $\exp(ipx)$ s are continuous as well as their first derivative.

Physically, however, $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability linked with conservation of momentum and product probability properties and so the continuity of $\exp(ipx)$ s is not only mathematical, but physical as these conservation or probability properties must be ensured. We stated in Part 2 that a photon which reflects at the n_1 - n_2 junction for $n_1 < n_2$ seems to sense the full possible interaction. Here we suggest that this may be physically possible due to the uncertainty in position of the incident at the n_1 - n_2 junction, i.e it might hit at $x=0$ or $x=0+dx$ which in turn leads to a resonance of all possible outcomes (together with the incident particle). In the 2-slit case, a resonance is formed between the particle interacting with one slit or the other in the same time interval (i.e. as a resonance).

Considerations of $\exp(ipx)$

We have argued in previous notes that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ may be obtained from Newtonian mechanics if one considers two-body elastic scattering. In such a case, given an initial (e_1, e_2)

and (p_1, p_2) vectors one may argue that any (e_i, e_j) and (p_i, p_j) pair should have the same product probability as long as energy and momentum are conserved. This might at first lead to $\exp(iE)$ and $\exp(ip)$, but if one reverses the x-axis direction, then $\exp(ip)$ and $\exp(-ip)$ should have the same value and they do not. Thus, we suggest the Lorentz invariant form:

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((1))$$

which is also time reversal invariant. We stress that even though ((1)) is a math function, it is also linked with conservation of momentum and the property of product probabilities listed above. We note that ((1)) is a complex unit modulus number because a free particle has no particular real weight.

Now $\exp(ipx)$ seems to imply an uncertainty or stochasticity in space for a given particle characterized by a wavelength $\hbar/|p|$. This is not simply mathematical, but physical as such a particle may interact with both slits of a 2-slit apparatus and create an interference pattern. We suggest that regardless of how the particle passes through the 2-slit system, it is the interaction which is important and it is stochastic, governed by an interaction with each slit, leading to a probabilistic OR situation:

$$\exp(i p \cdot r_1) + \exp(ip \cdot r_2) \quad ((2))$$

where r_1 and r_2 are vectors from the centers of each slit to a fixed point on a screen. We argue that there is a physical stochasticity linked with $\exp(ipx)$ (otherwise it would only "see" one slit), but the interaction with both slits leads to an entangled result ((2)) which means that there is a new physical stochastic resonance given by ((2)), while initially there was $\exp(ipx)$ if the slits lie along the y axis. ((2)) holds while the interaction occurs, and shows the full range of possible outcomes, but as soon as the photon leaves the 2-slit apparatus where it was interacting with both slits, it does so along a particular ray which is compatible with ((2)). In other words, the photon cannot move along rays which are linked with zeros of ((2)). Thus, the full interaction resonance ((2)) governs the outcome of a single photon.

We suggest that a similar idea holds for n_1 - n_2 reflection-refraction. In particular, in Part 2, we suggested that even if one has a photon which reflects from an n_1 - n_2 junction, if $n_1 < n_2$, then the reflected photon has a phase of $\exp(i \cdot 3.14) = -1$ which suggests that it sensed the full set of outcomes, just as ((2)) represents all outcome possibilities

Here, we try to investigate how this may be physically possible. We suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ of the incident photon means there is uncertainty in x linked to a p momentum hit. One may mathematically state that the n_1 - n_2 junction is at $x=0$ (and the math continuity is important), but physically the p hit may occur at a $x=0+dx$. (We have made this argument in previous notes.) This leads to two possible hit points and two continuity equations i.e

$$A\exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2x) \quad \text{at } x=0 \quad ((3a))$$

$$\text{and } A\exp(ipx) - pB\exp(-ipx) = C p_2 \exp(ip_2x) \quad \text{at } x=0 \quad ((3b))$$

Here AA, BB, CC are fluxes of the incident, reflected and refracted photons. As shown in Part 2, B must be negative if $n_1 < n_2$. In other words, the reflected photon picks up a phase of $\exp(i 3.14) = -1$ and this is physical as it will interfere with some photon with momentum $-p$ which does not have this phase.

Here we argue that if the reflected photon may interfere with some other photon, it is essentially interfering with the incident photon. In other words, the uncertainty in x (i.e. a dx) region means that one does not really know if one has an incident, reflected or refracted photon and one must consider all three. Continuity of $\exp(ipx)$ at $x=0$ and $x=0+dx$ is applied because $\exp(ipx)$ s are associated with conservation of momentum. As a result, whatever physical-stochastic property of the incident particle is at work, a phase of $\exp(i 3.14)$ must be induced in the reflected particle so it may physically-stochastically counteract the incident photon in the resonance which occurs in dx . In classical physics, one deals with positive, real numbers, but in quantum mechanics it seems that there is an inherent stochasticity with physical consequences. As a result, we suggest that adding $\exp(ipx)$ s for different time events really means that there is some kind of physical sampling actually occurring. In the case of the 2-slit apparatus, this sampling was of the form of interactions with both slits at the same time and in the n_1 - n_2 reflection-refraction case, it seems to be that one may have an incident, reflected or refracted photon at a given time and so one has a kind of resonance of all three, until the interaction ceases and a reflected or refracted photon is sent out and the incident photon is then gone.

Conclusion

In conclusion, classical probability involves OR scenarios which represent results which occur at different times. For example, if one tosses a coin, one has $1 = P(\text{heads}) + P(\text{tails})$ with each $P = .5$. A head, however, cannot occur at the same time as a tail. Furthermore, as argued in Parts 1 and 2, the stochasticity is in the toss.

With a quantum free particle, we argued in Part 2 that there is an inherent stochasticity in space associated with a particle. This allows it to interact with both slits in a 2-slit apparatus and create a resonance interaction state. One may write $\exp(ip \cdot r_1) + \exp(ip \cdot r_2)$ ((2)) which suggests events which occur at different times, but we suggest that the interactions with the two slits occur in the same time interval (as part of a resonance). Thus, all outcomes governed by $\exp(ipx)$ are part of the resonance, but as the particle moves away, it only follows one ray, but one which is compatible with ((2)).

We suggest that a similar process occurs for n_1 - n_2 junction reflection-refraction. In Part 2, we argued that even if a single photon reflects, if $n_1 < n_2$, the reflected photon picks up a phase of $\exp(i 3.14) = -1$. We argued that it is as if the photon senses both possible outcomes because the -1 factor is needed so that $B < 0$ in $A+B=C$ (as discussed above). In other words, the reflected photon somehow knows about the properties of the possible refracted one. Here we suggest that such a sampling of all possible outcomes is physically possible because as stated in previous notes, $\exp(ipx)$ means that the incident photon does not hit at a precise x . This means one may consider a junction at $x=0$ and $x=0+dx$ leading to two continuity equations. Within dx , one may have either an incident, reflected or refracted photon and one does not know which one is present. Thus, one must consider the relation between all three, i.e. all possible

outcomes. This must be consistent with both $A+B=C$ and $pA-pB=p_2C$. The first equation shows that B must be negative (see Part 2) and so the reflected photon must pick up a phase $\exp(i\pi)$ (3.1.4). This phase is physical and allows it to interfere with another photon with $-p$, but no phase. We suggest that it physically interacts with the incident photon, because similar to the 2-slit case, there is a resonance, but here it includes the incident, reflected and refracted photon. This resonance must satisfy the two continuity equations discussed, but then there is a single outcome (either reflection or refraction), but it must be compatible with the resonance results, just as the single ray path of a photon from a 2-slit apparatus must be compatible with the resonance of ((2))